

«DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN EDUCATION» USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS ON ENGLISH LESSONS

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ABSTRACT

It is significant that our nation is undergoing extensive reforms, including adjustments to the higher education system. Because raising the standard of education, solidifying the academic and technical foundation of higher education, and expanding access to higher education will all be crucial in elevating our nation to a position of prominence on the global stage. This post will talk about how authentic resources are used in English courses to develop modern education.

Over the past three years, the country has been developing regulations aimed at addressing the problems of improving the management and development of education with a system-innovative approach.

In accordance with the priorities of socio-economic development of the country, the Presidential Decree «On measures to further develop the system of higher education» dated April 20, 2017, to create the necessary conditions for the training of highly qualified specialists at the level of international standards. Serves to increase the material and technical base. Also, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 5, 2018 «On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in the ongoing comprehensive reforms in the country.» It is no exaggeration to say that the decision took the education system to a new level. This document, which is an important step

in the training of personnel, laid the foundation for the creation of adequate conditions for the development of the higher education system. In particular, the resolution identifies a number of problems that hinder the improvement of the quality of education in higher education institutions, as well as measures to address the existing pain points. In addition, the Action Strategy identifies important issues for the radical renewal of the content of training, the creation of the necessary conditions for the training of highly qualified specialists at the level of international standards.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 «On approval of the Concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030» raised the process of training highly qualified independent thinking to a qualitatively new level. Identified priorities for systemic

education reform. The goals of this document are to modernize higher education, as well as to develop the social sphere and the economy based on advanced educational technologies.

According to the decree, the number of state and non-state higher education institutions in the country will increase through the development of public-private partnership in higher education. This will be accompanied by the further development of a healthy competitive environment in the industry, which, as noted in the decree, will increase the enrollment of general secondary education graduates in higher education by more than 50 percent. Competition helps improve quality. Ultimately, it will help increase the number of highly qualified specialists in Uzbekistan and increase the level of higher education.

According to the decree, at least 10 higher education institutions in Uzbekistan will be included in the first 1000 places in the ranking of internationally recognized organizations (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Higher Education or Academic Ranking of World Universities). It is planned to include the National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University in the list of the first 500 places in the list of higher education institutions. The successful implementation of these goals will also lay the foundation for the development of the internationalization of education in Uzbekistan. The universities of our country will cooperate with prestigious foreign educational institutions to increase the exchange of students and teachers in academic and scientific fields.

This decree provides for raising the content of higher education to a

qualitatively new level, the establishment of a system of training highly qualified personnel who can make a worthy contribution to the sustainable development of the social sphere and the etc. Today, a new monitoring system for assessing the quality of education in our country is being formed based on the identification and comparison with the help of international assessment programs. Study of international experience in quality assessment of education, comparative and comprehensive analysis of the existing system, close cooperation with relevant international and foreign organizations, agencies, research institutions, implementation of international projects for quality assessment of education, modern improving the national evaluation system is important. Accordingly, on the basis of the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 8, 2018 «On measures to organize international research in the field of education quality assessment in the public education system» international research on education quality assessment under the State Inspectorate for Education Quality Control under the Cabinet of Ministers The National Center for Enhancement was established. Most importantly, on November 12, 2018, the State Inspectorate for Quality Control in Education under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Organization for International Cooperation and Development reached an agreement on participation in the International Student Assessment Program (PISA) 2021. . In turn, a brief overview of PISA research .In 2021, for the first time, our country will participate in the international survey PISA (International Program for Assessment of

Students aged 15-16). About 90 countries are participating in the study, conducted by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. Based on the results of this rating, the future development of our country will be assessed. The importance of this process for our developing country can be seen from the fact that large companies with long-term foreign investment take into account the results of this rating. A special center has been set up in our country by the government to conduct PISA and similar international research. During the meeting, information was provided on the activities of the center, the ongoing preparatory work, school readiness, inspections, seminars held in cooperation with the center, the Ministry of Public Education, the development of teaching aids. Ambitious goals such as Uzbekistan's successful participation in the PISA international survey in 2021 and joining the top 30 developed countries in the ranking of this program to assess student achievement in the field of education. It was noted in the concept of development of the limit system until 2030 PISA — Programme for International Student Assessment

PISA is a collaborative effort on the part of the member countries of the OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) to measure how well 15-year-olds are prepared to meet the challenges of today's knowledge societies. Over 40 countries, including Canada, and more than a quarter of a million students participate in this international assessment that occurs every three years. PISA assesses three domains: reading literacy, mathematical literacy, and scientific literacy.

How PISA Works

A sample of 15-year-old students is randomly chosen from selected schools in each country for the PISA assessment. PISA is a two-hour pen-and-paper assessment with both multiple-choice questions and questions requiring students to construct their own answers. Students and principals also complete a questionnaire. Each assessment examines one domain in depth, and the other two domains provide a summary profile of skills. Reading literacy was examined in depth in 2000, mathematical literacy will be examined in depth in 2003, and scientific literacy will be examined in depth in 2006.

Significance of PISA

The internationally comparable evidence on student performance can assist jurisdictions to bring about improvements in schooling to better prepare young people to enter a society of rapid change and global interdependence. As well, it can provide directions for policy development, For curricular and instructional efforts, and for student learning. Coupled with appropriate incentives, it can motivate students to learn better, teachers to teach better, and schools to be more effective. PISA represents an unprecedented effort to achieve comparability of results across countries, cultures, and languages. Approximately 30 000 15-year-old students from more than 1000 schools across Canada took part in the first administration of PISA in 2000. A large Canadian sample was drawn so that information could be provided at both national and provincial levels. Canadian students performed well in the global context, ranking second in reading, sixth in mathematics, and fifth in science.

SO WHAT MUST SCHOOLS DO The good results cannot come overnight. If we start

the journey today, then we are expecting another three to five years to show a tangible improvement. Improving PISA scores requires a paradigm shift in teaching and assessing. Assessment is the keyword. Schools must stop the traditional memory tests and provide a major modification in the questioning levels and styles. Train students to use alternative assessment strategies; such as self-assessment and providing narrative feedback in addition to the quantitative scores. These will give students a clearer idea of where they stand and where they want to go.

Schools must provide qualified trained teaching staff that is committed and can run with the vision to provide consistent learning habits. Moreover, there is a need for more Student-centered lessons that address the needs and interests of each student.

Developing and assessing students' cognitive and non-cognitive skills including problem-solving, analysis, and creativity are other major factors that should be considered. Transfer the learning responsibility to students and support their metacognitive skills and capacity to

set their goals and reflect constructively on their own learning.

The system of providing last minute test preparations for students as these externals tests approach, is not going to work and has it has been proven ineffective over time. The key is to start early, focus on the skills and not the test content and also ensure that students are fully aware that the skills they are gaining are for more than just test preparation, they are for life. In preparation for the next PISA assessment, two documents have been prepared, one for teachers and another for students. In this document for teachers, there are two examples for whole-class discussion and two sample tasks with answers and scoring criteria. In the companion document for students, the sample tasks are also provided but without answers and scoring criteria. These two documents are published to enable students, with the help of their teachers, to attain a clear understanding of the assessment and how it is scored and to help ensure more confident and successful participation. There is also a pamphlet for parents to raise awareness of the purpose, methodology, and significance of PISA.

References:

1. Abdilkadimovna, K. N. (2021). Comparative And Linguocultural Analysis Of The Concept" Gender" In Uzbek And English Languages. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(06), 112-117.
2. Komilova, N. A. (2022, June). COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL VERBALIZERS OF THE CONCEPT "GENDER" IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES. In *International Scientific and Current Research Conferences* (pp. 103-106).
3. Komilova, N. A. Comparative Analysis of "Gender" Concept and Issues of Gender Field in English and Uzbek Languages.
4. Мирзаахмедович, Х. Ғ., & Комилова, Н. А. (2021). ИНГЛИЗ ВА ЎЗБЕК ТИЛЛАРИДА ГЕНДЕР КОНЦЕПТУАЛ СЕМАНТИКАСИ ВЕРБАЛИЗАТОРЛАРИ НОМИНАТИВ ТУРЛАРИНИНГ ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 4(6).

5. Shodiyeva, G. N. Q. (2022). MATN GRAMMATIKASINING ASOSIY MUAMMOLARI. Academic research in educational sciences, 3(NUU Conference 2), 1173-1176.
6. Do'smatov, D., & qizi Shodiyeva, G. N. (2022, May). O 'ZBEK TILSHUNOSLIGIDA SO 'ZLARNI TURKUMLARGA AJRATISH TAMOYILLARI. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES ON LEARNING AND TEACHING (Vol. 1, No. 8, pp. 770-774).
7. Shodieva, G. N. Q., & Rakhmonova, M. A. Q. (2021). INFORMATION PERIOD CHANGE OF PEOPLE'S OUTLOOK, NEGATIVE AND POSITIVE IMPACT OF THE INTERNET. Scientific progress, 2(8), 563-566.
8. Najmiddinovna, R. Z., & Najmiddinovna, R. K. (2022). INNOVATIVE APPROACHES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(05), 19-21.